

MEAN-VARIANCE PORTFOLIO OPTIMIZATION BASED ON LEDOIT-WOLF SHRINKAGE WITH K-MEDOIDS CLUSTERING APPROACH FOR THE IDXBUMN20 INDEX

Kayla Azarya Putri Christanti Saranga¹, Agus Rusgiyono^{2*}, Abdul Hoyyi³

^{1,2,3} Department of Statistics, Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang, Indonesia

ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 15 June 2026</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Agus Rusgiyono</p>	<p>This study addresses the construction of an optimal stock portfolio under uncertainty in risk and return. It aims to optimize a portfolio from the IDXBUMN20 index using K-Medoids clustering for stock selection and the Mean-Variance Efficient Portfolio method with Ledoit–Wolf shrinkage to improve risk estimation stability. The data consist of daily closing prices of IDXBUMN20 stocks from August 2025 to February 2026. K-Medoids clustering is applied to 20 stocks based on financial performance indicators, including Return on Assets, Net Profit Margin, and Earnings per Share, to select representative stocks with the highest expected return from each cluster. Four representative stocks are obtained, and the optimal portfolio is constructed using the Mean-Variance approach with a Ledoit–Wolf covariance estimator, resulting in portfolio weights of BBTN (20.00%), TINS (19.68%), BBNI (40.63%), and PGEO (19.69%). Risk is measured using Historical Simulation Value at Risk at a 95% confidence level, indicating a controlled potential loss of 0.0269. Portfolio evaluation using the Sharpe Ratio yields a value of 0.1220, indicating that the combined approach produces an optimal portfolio.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Portfolio Optimization; K-Medoids; Mean-Variance Efficient Portfolio; Ledoit–Wolf Shrinkage; Value at Risk.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Investment is the activity of allocating funds to an asset with the expectation of obtaining profits in the future. In its development, investment has increasingly been carried out in financial assets, particularly stocks. This is in line with publications from the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX), which reported a significant increase in the number of capital market investors, reaching 11.42% compared to 2024. According to [1], stocks are investment instruments that provide potential returns in the form of capital gains and dividends but also involve risks. Investors should not allocate all their funds to a single asset in order to reduce investment risk [2]. Therefore, investors need to construct a stock portfolio, which is a collection or combination of various stocks [3].

An optimal portfolio is formed by combining several stocks to maximize returns and minimize risk, a concept theoretically explained by [4] through the Mean-Variance Model. However, the Mean-Variance Model requires the estimation of a covariance matrix and stable, accurate return data. In reality, financial data tend to be volatile and often deviate from classical assumptions due to their sensitivity to economic, political, and other factors [5].

The instability of data distributions causes sample covariance matrix estimates to become biased and fail to

represent the true covariance structure [6]. This is consistent with [7], who argued that the sensitivity of the Mean-Variance Model affects estimation errors in both risk and return, often resulting in extreme portfolio weights. To address this issue, a more stable covariance matrix estimation approach is needed to reduce estimation errors, one of which is the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage Estimator. This approach constructs a covariance matrix by combining the sample covariance matrix with a simpler target matrix. Research by [6] found that portfolios constructed using the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage Estimator achieved better performance compared to portfolios using other covariance estimation approaches. Therefore, this model is suitable for generating portfolios with improved performance.

In addition to the problem of estimation instability, investors also face complexity in selecting stocks from the many alternatives available in the market. Consequently, cluster analysis is needed to facilitate more efficient stock selection. K-Medoids clustering is a medoid-based clustering method in which a medoid represents the data point with the smallest total distance to all other points within a cluster [8]. Research by [9] showed that K-Medoids clustering outperformed other methods such as K-Means in selecting cluster centers and controlling the possibility of overlap between clusters. The clusters produced by K-Medoids tend to be more stable because the method is less

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affected by outliers, which are commonly found in economic data.

This study classifies stocks based on financial ratios of companies included in the IDXBUMN20 index using the K-Medoids Clustering algorithm. IDXBUMN20 is an index consisting of 20 State-Owned Enterprise (SOE) stocks listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. SOE stocks are attractive to investors because they generally exhibit high liquidity, large market capitalization, and strong regulatory compliance. The uncertainty and extreme data frequently observed in the Indonesian capital market are expected to be addressed through an optimal portfolio constructed using a combination of K-Medoids Clustering and the Mean-Variance portfolio model based on the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage covariance estimator applied to stocks in the IDXBUMN20 index.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Stock selection was carried out by grouping stocks based on financial ratio analysis. According to [10], ratio analysis is a technique used to analyze a company's financial statements through financial ratios in order to identify relationships between specific financial figures and other relevant values. The financial ratios used as clustering indicators in this study were Return on Assets (ROA), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Earnings per Share (EPS). Return on Assets (ROA) measures a company's ability to generate net income from its total assets and can be calculated using the following equation:

$$ROA = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Total assets}} \quad (1)$$

Net Profit Margin (NPM) can be calculated using the following equation:

$$NPM = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Net Sales}} \quad (2)$$

Earning per Share (EPS) can be calculated using the following equation:

$$EPS = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Outstanding Shares}} \quad (3)$$

Financial ratios have different units and scales, which may lead to bias in the analysis. Therefore, the data must be standardized to ensure a uniform and balanced scale across all variables. Data standardization can be performed using the Standard Scaler method, which is calculated as follows:

$$Z_{i,p} = \frac{X_{i,p} - \bar{X}_p}{S_p} \quad (4)$$

where:

X_i : original value of the i -th observation for the p -th variable

\bar{X}_p : mean value of the p -th variable

S_p : standard deviation of the p -th variable

$Z_{i,p}$: standardized value of the i -th observation for the p -th variable

K-Medoids cluster analysis is a data clustering method that uses actual observations within the dataset as medoids, or cluster centers. Therefore, this method is particularly suitable for datasets containing outliers. The detection of multivariate

outliers is performed using the Mahalanobis Distance. Mahalanobis Distance measures the distance of an observation from the data mean while taking into account the variance and correlation among variables. The Mahalanobis Distance can be calculated using the following equation:

$$D_i^2 = (\mathbf{x}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}})^T \mathbf{S}^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_i - \bar{\mathbf{x}}) \quad (5)$$

where:

\mathbf{x}_i : vector of values for all variables corresponding to the i -th observation

$\bar{\mathbf{x}}$: vector of mean values of all observations for each variable

\mathbf{S}^{-1} : inverse of the sample covariance matrix

A value of D_i^2 , or Mahalanobis Distance, is considered a multivariate outlier if it exceeds the critical value of the Chi-square distribution with p variables and a significance level of α . This criterion can be expressed as follows.

$$D_i^2 > \chi_{p,1-\frac{\alpha}{2}}^2 \quad (6)$$

K-Medoids cluster analysis requires several assumptions to be satisfied, namely sample adequacy and the absence of multicollinearity among variables [11].

a. Sample Adequacy

The Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) test is used as a measure of overall sample adequacy as well as the adequacy of individual variables. According to [12], the KMO statistic can be calculated using the following equation:

$$KMO = \frac{\sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{q=1; q \neq p}^P r_{pq}^2}{\sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{q=1; q \neq p}^P r_{ij}^2 + \sum_{p=1}^P \sum_{q=1; q \neq p}^P a_{pq}^2} \quad (7)$$

where:

r_{pq} : correlation coefficient between variables p and q

a_{pq} : partial correlation coefficient between variables p and q

A sample is considered representative of the population if the KMO value falls between 0.50 and 1.00.

b. Non-Multikolinierity

The presence of multicollinearity can be identified by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). According to [13], the VIF value can be computed using the following equation:

$$VIF_p = \frac{1}{1 - R_p^2} \quad (8)$$

where:

R_p^2 : coefficient of determination of the p -th independent variable regressed on the remaining independent variables

VIF_p : Variance Inflation Factor for the p -th independent variable with respect to all other independent variables

The K-Medoids clustering algorithm can be implemented through the following steps:

1. Determine the number of clusters (k) to be formed. Given n observations, the possible number of clusters is defined as $k = 2, 3, \dots, n - 1$.
2. Randomly select k observations as the initial medoids, resulting in a set of medoids denoted as $M = \{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k\}$.

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3. Assign each observation x_j to the nearest cluster based on the distance function $d(x_j, m_i)$, which is calculated using the Euclidean distance:

$$d(x_j, m_i) = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^p (x_{jp} - m_{ip})^2} \quad (9)$$

thus,

$$x_j \in C_i \text{ if } d(x_j, m_i) = \min_{1 \leq h \leq k} d(x_j, m_h) \quad (10)$$

where:

- x_j : the j -th observation
- m_i : the medoid of the i -th cluster
- x_{jp} : the value of the j -th observation on the p -th variable
- m_{ip} : Medoid

4. Compute the total within-cluster distance as follows

$$D' = \sum_{i=1}^k D_i \quad (11)$$

where

$$D_i = \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} d(x_j, m_i) \quad (12)$$

where:

- D' : total distance
- D_i : total distance within cluster i
- $d(x_j, m_i)$: distance between observation j and the medoid of cluster i
- k : number of clusters
- n_i : number of observations in cluster i

5. Randomly select a new set of k observations as candidate medoids.
6. Reassign each observation to the nearest medoid based on the Euclidean distance defined in Equation (9).
7. Calculate the new total distance using Equations (11) and (12).
8. Compute the difference between the new and previous total distances as follows.

$$D = D'' - D' \quad (13)$$

where:

- D : difference in total distance
- D'' : total distance obtained from the new medoids

9. If $D < 0$, replace the current medoids with the new medoids, as the clustering solution has improved.
10. Repeat steps 2–8 until convergence, that is, when $D > 0$ or when no further medoid replacement occurs.

According to [15], the optimal number of clusters (k) can be determined using the Silhouette Coefficient, which is calculated as follows:

$$SC = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max\{a(i), b(i)\}} \quad (14)$$

where:

- $a(i)$: the average distance between observation i and all other observations within the same cluster

- $b(i)$: the minimum average distance between observation i and all observations belonging to a different cluster
- n : the total number of observations

The stocks included in the portfolio are selected from each resulting cluster based on the highest expected return. Return represents the gain or reward received by investors as compensation for bearing investment risk [16]. Stock returns can be classified into two categories: realized return and expected return. According to [17], the realized return can be calculated using the logarithmic return formula as follows:

$$R_{i,t} = \ln\left(\frac{P_{i,t}}{P_{i,t-1}}\right), P_{i,t} > 0 \quad (15)$$

Expected return refers to the return that investors anticipate receiving in the future. It can be estimated as the arithmetic mean of historical returns and is calculated as follows:

$$E(R_i) = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T R_{i,t}}{T} \quad (16)$$

where:

- $R_{i,t}$: realized return of stock i during period t
- $P_{i,t}$: closing price of stock i in period t
- $P_{i,t-1}$: closing price of stock i in period $t - 1$
- $E(r_i)$: expected return of stock i
- T : number of observation periods

The construction of an optimal portfolio involves determining the proportion of funds allocated to each stock included in the portfolio. Portfolio weights are estimated using the Mean-Variance optimization model, with the covariance matrix estimated through the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage approach. According to [6], covariance estimation using the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage method is carried out through the following steps:

1. Compute the Sample Covariance Matrix (S) based on the stock return data.
2. Define the shrinkage target F

$$F = \bar{s}I \quad (17)$$

with

$$\bar{s} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N S_{ii} \quad (18)$$

where:

- F : target covariance matrix
- I : identity matrix
- N : number of stocks
- S_{ii} : variance of the i -th stock
- \bar{s} : average of the diagonal elements of the sample covariance matrix

3. Estimate the shrinkage intensity

$$\hat{\lambda} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \widehat{\text{var}}(S_{ij})}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (S_{ij} - F_{ij})^2} \quad (19)$$

with:

$$\widehat{\text{var}}(S_{ij}) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (r_{ti} r_{tj} - S_{ij})^2 \quad (20)$$

where:

- S_{ij} : element (i, j) of the sample covariance matrix
- F_{ij} : element (i, j) of the target matrix
- r_{ti} : return of stock i in period t
- r_{tj} : return of stock j in period t

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- T : number of return observation periods
4. Compute the Ledoit-Wolf Covariance Estimator
- $$\Sigma_{LW} = (1 - \hat{\lambda})S + \hat{\lambda}F \quad (21)$$

The resulting Σ_{LW} serves as a more stable and reliable alternative to the sample covariance matrix. After obtaining the Ledoit-Wolf covariance matrix, it is used as an input in the Mean-Variance optimization model to determine the optimal portfolio weights. The portfolio weights are calculated as follows:

$$w = \frac{\Sigma_{LW}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_N}{\mathbf{1}_N^T \Sigma_{LW}^{-1} \mathbf{1}_N} \quad (22)$$

where:

- w : vector of the portfolio weight
- Σ_{LW}^{-1} : inverse of the Ledoit-Wolf covariance matrix
- $\mathbf{1}_N$: $N \times 1$ vector of ones
- $\mathbf{1}_N^T$: transpose of the vector of ones, with dimension $1 \times N$

The Historical Simulation Value at Risk (VaR) method was employed to estimate the maximum potential loss arising from market risk. According to [17], the calculation of VaR using the Historical Simulation approach involves the following steps:

1. Calculate the stock return.
 2. Rank the returns according to their losses, from the largest loss to the smallest.
 3. Determine the percentile of the historical return distribution corresponding to the selected significance level (α).
 4. Calculate the Value at Risk over the specified holding period at a confidence level of $(1-\alpha)$ using the following formula
- $$VaR = V_0(r_{100\alpha}) \sqrt{t} \quad (23)$$

where:

- VaR : maximum potential loss
- V_0 : initial investment value
- $r_{100\alpha}$: return corresponding to the $\alpha(100)$ -th percentile of the return distribution
- t : holding period

Portfolio performance was evaluated using the Sharpe Ratio, which measures the excess return generated by a portfolio relative to the risk undertaken. The Sharpe Ratio compares the portfolio's expected return with the risk-free rate and standardizes the result by the portfolio's risk, as follows:

$$SR_p = \frac{E(R_p) - R_f}{Sd_p} \quad (24)$$

where:

- SR_p : Sharpe Ratio of the portfolio
- $E(R_p)$: expected portfolio return
- R_f : risk-free rate of return
- Sd_p : standard deviation of portfolio returns

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilizes secondary data in the form of 2024 financial ratios from 20 companies included in the IDXBUMN20 Index during the period of August 2025 to February 2026. The data were obtained from the Indonesia Stock

Exchange (IDX). In addition, the study uses daily stock closing price data collected from Yahoo Finance covering the period from May 2025 to October 2025, as well as Bank Indonesia publications, specifically the BI Interest Rate for October 2025, which serves as the risk-free rate.

The variables used in this study include Return on Assets (ROA), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Earnings per Share (EPS). Data analysis was conducted using RStudio and Microsoft Excel through the following stages:

1. Collecting and preparing financial ratio data of companies, consisting of Return on Assets (ROA), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Earnings per Share (EPS).
2. Standardizing the data using the Standard Scaler method to ensure that all variables are measured on a comparable scale and to eliminate bias caused by differences in units and magnitudes among variables.
3. Detecting multivariate outliers using Mahalanobis Distance to identify observations that deviate substantially from the overall data structure when all variables are considered simultaneously.
4. Testing the assumptions required for cluster analysis, including assessing sample adequacy (representative sample detection), and examining the absence of multicollinearity among variables, to ensure that the variables provide unique information and do not exhibit excessive linear relationships.
5. Measuring the distance between observations using Euclidean Distance, which serves as the similarity measure in the clustering process.
6. Performing stock cluster analysis using the K-Medoids Clustering algorithm, which groups stocks according to similarities in their financial characteristics.
7. Determining the optimal number of clusters using the Silhouette Coefficient method, where the clustering solution with the highest Silhouette value is selected as the most appropriate grouping structure.
8. Selecting representative stocks from each cluster based on the highest expected return, so that each cluster contributes one stock candidate for portfolio formation.
9. Calculating the mean return vector, sample covariance matrix, and correlation coefficients among stocks, which serve as the fundamental inputs for portfolio optimization.
10. Estimating the covariance matrix using the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage method, which improves the stability and reliability of covariance estimation by shrinking the sample covariance matrix toward a structured target matrix.
11. Constructing the optimal portfolio and determining the investment weights for each stock using the Mean-Variance approach, with the objective of achieving the best trade-off between expected return and risk.

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12. Estimating Value at Risk (VaR) using the Historical Simulation method, to measure the maximum potential loss of the portfolio at a specified confidence level and holding period.
13. Evaluating portfolio performance using the Sharpe Ratio, which assesses the portfolio's ability to generate excess returns relative to the risk assumed by investors.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The construction of the optimal portfolio began with the selection of stocks to be included in the portfolio. Stock selection was carried out using K-Medoids cluster analysis based on three financial performance indicators, namely Return on Assets (ROA), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Earnings per Share (EPS), for companies listed in the IDXBUMN20 Index. The descriptive statistics of these variables are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Financial Ratios

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
ROA	0,2287	12,2995	4,0515	3,7339
NPM	0,6533	39,3738	14,2202	10,4388
EPS	2,0570	774,3200	236,4660	225,4698

As shown in Table 1, the variables have different measurement units and scales. Therefore, data standardization was performed using Equation (4). The standardized data are presented in Table 2. Following standardization, all variables were transformed to a comparable scale, making them suitable for subsequent analysis.

Table 2. Standardized Data

Stock	ROA	NPM	EPS
ADHI	-0.8702	-1.1605	-0.9005
AGRO	-0.9812	-1.0528	-1.0396
ANTM	1.2321	-0.8289	-0.3378
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
TLKM	1.6624	0.6016	0.3276

After standardization, multivariate outlier detection was conducted to examine whether the dataset contained any multivariate outliers. The detection procedure was performed using the Mahalanobis Distance as defined in Equation (5), and the results are presented in Table 3. The results indicate that one observation exceeded the tolerance threshold and was identified as a multivariate outlier. This finding supports the use of K-Medoids clustering, as the method is more robust to outliers than alternative clustering approaches and is therefore appropriate for the cluster analysis conducted in this study.

Table 3. Results of Multivariate Outlier Detection

<i>i</i>	Stock	D_i^2	Multivariate Outlier
1	ADHI	1,9857	Not an Outlier
2	AGRO	2,1058	Not an Outlier
3	ANTM	2,5674	Not an Outlier
4	BBNI	3,2157	Not an Outlier

5	BBRI	0,9334	Not an Outlier
6	BBTN	1,0711	Not an Outlier
7	BJBR	1,0554	Not an Outlier
8	BJTM	0,9973	Not an Outlier
9	BMRI	4,7633	Not an Outlier
10	BRIS	1,9525	Not an Outlier
11	ELSA	1,6043	Not an Outlier
12	JSMR	6,2148	Not an Outlier
13	MTEL	2,6217	Not an Outlier
14	PGAS	0,7569	Not an Outlier
15	PGEO	9,7424	Outlier
16	PTBA	5,7093	Not an Outlier
17	PTPP	2,5268	Not an Outlier
18	SMGR	1,7911	Not an Outlier
19	TINS	2,4389	Not an Outlier
20	TLKM	2,9457	Not an Outlier

Prior to conducting the cluster analysis, sample adequacy and multicollinearity tests were performed to ensure that the data satisfied the assumptions required for clustering. Sample adequacy was assessed using the Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure. Based on the calculation using Equation (7), a KMO value of 0.5500 was obtained, which exceeds the minimum threshold of 0.5000. Therefore, the dataset was considered adequate and representative for cluster analysis. The absence of multicollinearity was evaluated by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for each variable using Equation (8). The results are presented in Table 4. Since none of the VIF values exceeded the threshold value of 10, all variables were considered free from multicollinearity.

Table 4. VIF

Variable	VIF
ROA	1,0468
NPM	1,2159
EPS	1,2470

After verifying the assumptions, cluster analysis was conducted using the K-Medoids algorithm with the Euclidean distance measure. The number of clusters (*k*) considered in the clustering process ranged from 2 to $n - 1$, where *n* represents the number of observations. Since the dataset consisted of 20 stocks listed in the IDXBUMN20 Index, the values of *k* examined in this study were 2,3,4, ...,19. The clustering results were evaluated using the Silhouette Coefficient, as presented in Table 5. The highest Silhouette Coefficient value, 0.4775, was obtained when the number of clusters was set to four, indicating that the four-cluster solution provided the best clustering structure.

Table 5. Silhouette Coefficient

Number of Clusters	Silhouette Coefficient
2	0,3215
3	0,4385

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4	0,4775
5	0,4428
6	0,4391
7	0,4397
8	0,4002
9	0,3389
10	0,3008
11	0,2934
12	0,2498
13	0,2263
14	0,2116
15	0,1914
16	0,1679
17	0,1220
18	0,0741
19	0,0121

The clustering analysis grouped stocks according to similarities in their financial characteristics, such that stocks within the same cluster exhibited relatively homogeneous characteristics while differing from those in other clusters. The resulting clusters served as the basis for selecting stocks to be included in the portfolio. Based on the clustering results, four optimal clusters were identified. Consequently, the portfolio was constructed using four representative stocks, one from each cluster. The representative stock from each cluster was selected based on the highest expected return. Expected returns were calculated using Equation (16), and the results are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Expected Return

Cluster	Stock	Expected Return
1	ADHI	-0,0002
	AGRO	0,0004
	BBTN	0,0014
	BJBR	-0,0004
	PTPP	-0,0001
	SMGR	0,0006
2	ANTM	0,0026
	ELSA	0,0008
	PGAS	0,0006
	PTBA	-0,0010
	TINS	0,0074
	TLKM	0,0016
3	BBNI	0,0004
	BBRI	0,0001
	BMRI	-0,0003
	JSMR	-0,0013
	BJTM	0,0003
4	BRIS	-0,0009
	MTEL	-0,0008
	PGEO	0,0029

Based on these results, BBTN was selected as the representative stock of Cluster 1, TINS as the representative stock of Cluster 2,

BBNI as the representative stock of Cluster 3, and PGEO as the representative stock of Cluster 4. The optimal portfolio was subsequently constructed using the Mean-Variance optimization framework with Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage covariance estimation. The procedure began by computing the sample covariance matrix and then re-estimating it using the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage method to obtain a more stable covariance estimator. Based on the calculations, the resulting Ledoit-Wolf covariance matrix was obtained as follows:

$$\Sigma_{LW} = \begin{bmatrix} 0,0010 & -0,0001 & 0,0004 & 0,0001 \\ -0,0001 & 0,0017 & 0,0000 & 0,0002 \\ 0,0004 & 0,0000 & 0,0006 & 0,0001 \\ 0,0001 & 0,0002 & 0,0001 & 0,0013 \end{bmatrix}$$

The Ledoit-Wolf covariance matrix was subsequently incorporated into the Mean-Variance optimization process to determine the optimal investment weights for each selected stock. Portfolio weights were calculated using Equation (22), and the results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Portfolio Weights

Stock	Weight
BBTN	0,2000
TINS	0,1968
BBNI	0,4063
PGEO	0,1969

After the optimal portfolio and its corresponding weights had been determined, the portfolio risk was evaluated using the Historical Simulation Value at Risk (VaR) method to estimate the maximum potential loss. VaR was calculated using Equation (23). Assuming an investment value of IDR 1,000,000, a 95% confidence level ($\alpha = 5\%$), and a one-day holding period, the estimated Value at Risk was IDR 26,895.89. This result implies that, with a confidence level of 95%, the maximum loss expected over the next trading day is approximately IDR 26,895.89.

Portfolio performance was subsequently evaluated using the Sharpe Ratio. The Sharpe Ratio was calculated using Equation (24), employing an annual risk-free rate of 4.75%, which was converted into a daily rate based on 252 trading days per year. The calculation yielded a Sharpe Ratio of 0.1220. This value indicates that, for every unit of risk assumed, the portfolio generates an excess return of 0.1220 above the risk-free rate per trading day. Therefore, the portfolio demonstrates a positive risk-adjusted performance, suggesting that the combination of K-Medoids Clustering, Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage, and Mean-Variance optimization is effective in constructing an efficient investment portfolio.

V. CONCLUSION

The construction of the optimal portfolio in this study was carried out using the Mean-Variance method based on Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage with a K-Medoids Clustering approach. The K-Medoids Clustering method was employed to group stocks according to their financial performance characteristics, as

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measured by Return on Assets (ROA), Net Profit Margin (NPM), and Earnings per Share (EPS). This process enabled the selection of representative stocks from each cluster based on the highest expected return, which were subsequently used as candidates for portfolio formation.

The optimal portfolio was then constructed using the Mean-Variance Efficient Portfolio method, with the covariance matrix estimated through the Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage approach. The optimization results indicate that the application of Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage produced a well-diversified and balanced portfolio allocation, consisting of BBTN (20.00%), TINS (19.68%), BBNI (40.63%), and PGEO (19.69%).

Portfolio risk was evaluated using Value at Risk (VaR) based on the Historical Simulation method at a 95% confidence level. The results show that the portfolio optimized using Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage exhibited a relatively controlled maximum potential loss of -0.0269. Portfolio performance was further assessed using the Sharpe Ratio, which yielded a value of 0.1220. This result indicates that the constructed portfolio was efficient in generating returns relative to the level of risk undertaken. Overall, the findings suggest that the combination of K-Medoids Clustering, Ledoit-Wolf Shrinkage, and the Mean-Variance Efficient Portfolio approach is capable of producing an optimal portfolio.

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